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**From War Wounds to Welfare: Caring for Albania's
Elderly in the Transition to Socialism (1945 – 1948)¹**

Abstract: *This article explores Albania's socialist regime's efforts in addressing post-war societal challenges, particularly housing impoverished elderly individuals in Shkodër's nursing home. It highlights disparities in the treatment of the elderly compared to children, focusing on their sacrifices and the neglect of their emotional and cultural needs. Healthcare provisions and cultural neglect within institutions like the nursing home are emphasized, underscoring the regime's differential treatment of age groups. The article reflects on the regime's privileging of specific categories, the scarcity of medical professionals, and the emotional and cultural void experienced by the elderly, drawing comparisons to practices during the monarchical regime in Albania.*

Keywords: *Socialist Regime; Elderly Care; Healthcare Disparities; Cultural Neglect; Age-Based Differential Treatment.*

Introduction

Usually, when studying the socialist period, especially the initial years of the new regime's establishment in Albania and other countries within the Socialist Bloc, significant attention is placed on the repressive aspects of the new regime. Consequently, rightful emphasis is given to extrajudicial executions of political opponents, nationalization of wealth, efforts towards solidifying the regime's power, and establishing a legal order of the so-called "dictatorship of the proletariat".

However, especially concerning the Albanian regime, there is somewhat less focus on the fact that immediately following the Second World War, the country was severely devastated by the conflict, having suffered damaged infrastructure and numerous casualties which left many children orphaned and many elderly people alone. Moreover, pre-

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war Albania was a semi-feudal country with an agrarian economic structure which lacked industrial development. The war, coupled with the preceding circumstances, resulted in considerable economic and social hardships, pushing the nation to the brink of famine. Therefore, the new government's immediate priorities involved combating hunger and addressing these social wounds caused by the war. Simultaneously, the holistic approach of the regime aimed to gradually integrate all state, public, and private institutions, including those in social care, under its umbrella.

This article aims to analyze the efforts of Albanian institutions, especially the Red Cross, to accommodate impoverished and lonely individuals in social care institutions during the post-war years, 1945 – 1948, with a particular focus on solitary elders. These initial post-war years represent a break from the old regime. Additionally, it's a transitional period for institutions and their organization, shifting from the inherited Italian model to the newly Yugoslav/Soviet model. Economically, these years were particularly challenging for the country due to the devastation of the war, which severely limited the state's capabilities to mitigate the social wounds arising from the war.

In 1945, the new regime inherited only one nursing home in Shkodër – the most important city of northern Albania – established during the fascist occupation, with a capacity for up to 120 individuals, despite significantly higher demand. Therefore, this article will also analyze how state authorities sought to fulfill the demands of individuals seeking shelter in this institution. This article will further endeavor to analyze their treatment in this institution, both in terms of material aspects like food and clothing, as well as healthcare and social care, and the cultural activities or lack thereof that affected these seniors. Thus, apart from the admission process in the nursing home, the paper will also try to analyze, the living conditions and treatment of the elders who lived in this institution. While the primary focus of the article is on the elders housed in the nursing home in Shkodër, occasional comparisons will be made between their admission and treatment in that institution and the admission and treatment of orphaned children in residential care for children. Since nursing home and orphanages fall under the same institutions – the Red Cross before 1948, and thereafter, the Directorate of Social Care – in most of the documents produced by these institutions or other state bodies like the Council of Ministers or Executive Committees, these issues are often raised together, sometimes compared, even though the solutions provided were usually different. On the other hand, as will be seen below, while the socialist regime placed great emphasis on political and

cultural education for children and young people, for the elderly this was almost nonexistent.

This paper will mainly rely on archival documents; therefore, the primary method will be analytical, critically examining and scrutinizing archival sources. Additionally, other sources like newspaper articles, and writings about important figures of the time will be utilized.

To provide a more complete picture of post-World War II Albania and to analyze the treatment of the elderly in Shkoder's nursing home as part of the general policies of the socialist regime in Albania, the first part of the article will present an overview of the political, economic, and social challenges in the country during that period. Therefore, apart from the aforementioned sources, the article will also draw from the secondary literature on these themes and similar topics.

Albania after World War II: Legal order, political situation, and economic challenges

Albania was liberated from German occupiers in November 1944, and power was assumed by the partisans led by the Albanian Communist Party. In December of 1945, general elections were held for the Constituent Assembly, which would determine the form of governance in the country. Until then, Albania had been a monarchy, which did not align with the regime desired by the communists. Only one political organization, the Democratic Front, participated in these elections, effectively a facade for the Communist Party, controlling it from within, although within the Front, there were individuals with anti-fascist activity and of varying non-communist political convictions. Post-election, these individuals, although elected as representatives through popular vote, were eliminated in three major judicial trials from 1946 to 1948, based on accusations of attempting to overturn the "people's power."

In January 1946, the Constituent Assembly declared Albania a "people's republic," and in March 1946, the status/constitution of the republic became the legal basis for the socialist regime established in Albania. However, even before the Constitution was adopted, between November 1944 and March 1946, the new regime institutions undertook a series of significant measures in political, economic, military, social, artistic, and cultural domains, grounded in the "rights of the victors of the war." It can be asserted that during this period (1944 – 1946), the new regime extended its power over all central and local organs and institutions in the country, including social care institutions such as the Red Cross, children's homes (orphanages), or the nursing home in Shkodër.

The Constitution and subsequent legislative acts were legal endorsements of actions already undertaken. (Krasniqi 2021: 3-4)

While endeavoring, quite successfully, to gain control over all structures entities and institutions in the country, the new regime faced a notably challenging situation: an economic crisis that risked transforming into a famine crisis and could potentially evoke significant societal discontent. In the 1940s, Albania's economy was in a severely distressed state. Primarily, this was linked to the longstanding economic backwardness from Albania's independence (1912) until the late 1930s, characterized by an agrarian, semi-feudal economic structure which was devoid of any significant industry and had limited trade. However, it was further exacerbated by the Second World War, which, apart from its human toll, inflicted substantial material damage on the country. This was reflected in difficulties in supplying basic goods to the population, such as bread, grains, essential clothing, salt, oil, soap, and other necessities. (Gjeçovi 2006: 95-96)

In this emergent post-war situation, the country urgently needed to rely on aid and credits from other countries of the Socialist Bloc, particularly the Yugoslavia and Soviet Union, as relations with other allied powers - the United States and Great Britain - were cooling. However, in the years 1945-1947, the immediate post-war period during which even the Soviet Union itself emerged with entirely devastated infrastructure and a troubled economic state, Albania's economic survival relied on the assistance provided by the United Nations Relief and Rehabilitation Administration (UNRRA). The survival of the Albanian population and a certain revival of the economy during this time were entirely contingent upon the free aid that UNRRA supplied to the country, primarily in wheat, flour, other agricultural products, as well as new machinery and raw materials. Overall, the assistance provided by UNRRA to Albania during this period is estimated at around thirty-two million US dollars, which saved the country from famine. (Kaba 2000: 139, 150, 157)

Despite the aid provided by UNRRA during the initial two years after liberation, the Albanian leadership, initially under Yugoslav influence until 1948, and later under Soviet influence, worsened relations not only with the UNRRA mission in the country but also with the governments of the United States and the United Kingdom, the main providers of UNRRA's donations, although the blame for the worsening of relations cannot be solely attributed to the Albanian government. By 1947, the UNRRA mission had withdrawn from Albania, and its assistance had ceased. In this situation, representatives of the Albanian government,

including Prime Minister Enver Hoxha himself, appealed for assistance primarily to the Soviet Union, as well as other countries within the Socialist Bloc, notably Yugoslavia until 1948.

These requests had been initiated as early as 1945 when Hoxha wrote to the Soviet Foreign Minister Vyacheslav Molotov, stating that without credit and grain assistance from the Soviet Union, Albania was at risk of famine. These and subsequent requests made by the Albanian government were generally approved by the Soviet Union. Throughout the period from 1945 to 1961, Albania received both credit and to some extent aid from the Soviets and other countries within the bloc which, however, bore interest following the breakdown of relations. (Boriçi 2022: 152, 154, 161)

Much has been discussed and written since 1991, as well as prior, both by Western political analysts and Albania's international allies such as the Soviet Union and China, and even by dissenting voices within the Albanian political leadership, regarding the misguided orientation of the Albanian economy during the socialist period (1945 – 1991). These critiques, largely warranted, primarily highlight substantial investments in heavy and mineral industries, oil extraction, and metallurgy, investments made at the expense of the population's welfare, reflected in the lack of improvement in Albanians' standard of living. It is beyond the scope of this article's intent to assess the economic policy of the Albanian state during socialism. However, what becomes evident from the requests for credit and economic assistance from socialist countries and from investment in various economic sectors is that while the absolute priority of the Albanian political leadership was heavy industry and minerals, they never entirely diverted attention from meeting the basic needs of the population. This is apparent in the initial requests made by Enver Hoxha to the Soviets and Yugoslavs, as well as from UNRRA in its early stages, where alongside machinery and raw materials for industry, urgent requests were made for wheat and other food products. (Boriçi 2022: 154-55, 163, 167)

These loans and investments made it possible for Albania not to suffer massive famine, despite the very low standard of living in the country, the rationing system of bread, food, and other consumer goods was officially lifted only in 1957. However, scarcity remained a characteristic of the entire 45-year period of the socialist system. Nonetheless, Albania did not face mass famine that could have resulted in deaths from starvation, unlike the Soviet Union (1930 – 1933) or China (1959 – 1961). This is linked to an important aspect of the Albanian Stalinist re-

gime – its social character. Apart from the violence of the repressive state apparatus with its despotic-bureaucratic nature, the modernizing role and the social character of the state are two significant aspects of this regime. (Meksi 2015: 243-245)

As a result, despite the state's economic difficulties, its social objectives were extensive, aiming to provide citizens with services from birth to death. Undoubtedly, both the quantity and quality of these services, as well as the goods the state could provide, were rather limited, but they represented basic support that all citizens were officially entitled to enjoy. As part of this social care that the state extended to its citizens, it established numerous social care institutions such as nurseries, kindergartens, canteens, holiday camps, nursing homes, and asylums, attempting to address a wide range of societal needs. Expenditures for these institutions, along with other instruments like pensions, scholarships, social assistance, constituted a significant portion of the state budget, in addition to the expenses incurred from loans acquired from other countries within the bloc. This comprehensive yet basic level of social care was one of the primary methods used to legitimize the regime in the eyes of the people, emphasizing the paternalistic position of the state – and its leaders, particularly the top leadership – toward the people. (Meksi 2015: 244-245)

Social wounds in post-WWII Albania and the struggle for their relief

In the early post-World War II years, due to the economic difficulties previously mentioned, the Albanian state faced challenges in fulfilling the role of social welfare support for all vulnerable groups. Nevertheless, partly due to the need to increase legitimacy among the broader population and to preempt any potential popular unrest due to extreme poverty verging on famine, some measures needed to be taken. Efforts were made through the Red Cross, an organization that had previously been the primary body attempting to alleviate the wounds of poverty and war in the country both before and during the conflict (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar n.d.).

Qamil Çela (1896 – 1988), a left-leaning former political emigrant, was appointed as the head of the Red Cross after the war (1945 – 1951). During his tenure, the organization primarily aimed to fulfill the need for food and clothing for the war-affected population. Due to the economic hardships in the country, urgent campaigns were conducted both domestically and among economic emigrants in France and the United States to

raise funds and material aid for the organization and its affiliates (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar n.d.).

A longstanding figure in Albanian political life, Çela had been involved in public affairs since the last years of Ottoman rule in Albanian territories, and maintained left-leaning political activity both within and outside the country during the 1920s – 1940s. As evidenced by testimonies, he appears to have been a humanitarian figure. During his political emigration to Italy and France (during the monarchical regime in Albania), he had endeavored to aid Albanians confined to emigrant camps there. During his leadership of the Albanian Red Cross, Çela drew on his connections abroad to attempt to alleviate the severe social wounds inflicted by the war. (Dylgjeri 2014)

His later life was challenging as he faced conflicts with the Albanian leadership, notably with Enver Hoxha personally, in the context of the harsh “class struggle” policy employed by the Albanian Stalinist regime. As a result, he was demoted and lived in partial isolation. He himself opposed this policy, even during his tenure leading the Red Cross, calling for the recruitment to the organization of individuals considered to come from the “overthrown classes”, but who possessed the necessary education or extensive experience in healthcare or social care. (Dylgjeri 2014).

The International Red Cross, along with religious communities in Albania, initiated campaigns to aid the destitute and war-affected people. In the *Jeta Kristiane* (The Christian Life) newspaper, the official organ of the Orthodox Church of Albania, both the editorial board and Archbishop Kristofor Kisi issued calls through sermons and articles urging people to contribute as much as possible to help those left homeless and without an income due to the war, especially orphaned children and elderly individuals living in isolation (Archbishop Kristofor 1944: 9-11). During this period, the Red Cross also made efforts towards healthcare campaigns, vaccination initiatives, treatment of infectious diseases, and the establishment of emergency aid courses, as well as addressing the shortage of medical staff and nurses in the country (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar n.d.).

In addition to poverty and the extensively damaged infrastructure caused by World War II, Albania was faced with a large orphaned population as children lost parents during the conflict, and many of the elderly lacked relatives and any means of livelihood. Hence, it became the responsibility of the Albanian Red Cross to care for these two social categories severely impacted by the war. This because the nursing home and orphanages in the country were administered by the Red Cross, which

was also the main organization for providing humanitarian aid to population. (Brisku 2023: 75)

Despite the significant need for shelter in these institutions such as the nursing home for the elderly and the orphanage, the capacities of the Red Cross were severely limited. Both the elderly home and the orphanages had a limited number of available spaces. Consequently, in a letter to the Prime Minister's office in July 1946, the president of the Red Cross, Qamil Çela, warned that there were frequent requests coming to his institution to admit orphaned children into the orphanage and lonely elderly individuals into the Nursing Home in Shkodër, but due to the lack of available spaces they could no longer accommodate new individuals. Despite this, the letter from the Red Cross also appealed to the Prime Minister's office to issue a circular to all prefectures, instructing them to keep these requests along with the relevant documentation archived. In the event of vacancies, the Red Cross leadership would then send each prefecture the corresponding number of spaces available for the elderly and children to be admitted to the Nursing Homes and orphanages (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p.1, 1946).²

The Prime Minister's office forwarded the Red Cross request to the Executive Committees of the districts. Additionally, the Prime Minister's office they emphasized that children of the National Liberation Anti-Fascist War martyrs³ were to be given special priority for accommodation in children's homes. Widowed parents (especially mothers) whose spouses were martyred in the Anti-Fascist War were also to be given priority for admission to the Nursing Home in Shkodër (CSA, F. 490, Fl. 416, p.2, 1946).

In October 1946, the Red Cross Executive Board sent another request to the Prime Minister's office, accompanied by a circular specifying the required documents for candidates seeking shelter in the nursing home. The documents included a written application by the candidate, a family certificate issued by the Civil Status Office, a poverty certificate issued by the National Liberation Anti-Fascist District Council and en-

² CSA-Central State Archive [of Albania], F-Fonds, Fl-File.

³ In the original document, the word "dëshmor" (from Alb.: martyr) is used, which, if we refer to the Albanian Language Dictionary, denotes "one who sacrifices their life for the freedom and social justice, for the good of the people and the homeland." This term has been in use in Albanian public discourse since the period of the National Renaissance (1850s – 1912) in connection with individuals who were murdered in efforts for the freedom and independence of the country from the Ottoman Empire, or for the free use of the Albanian language.

dorsed by the Executive Committee of the Sub-Prefecture, as well as a medical-legal report stating that the candidate did not suffer from infectious diseases or severe psycho-physical impairments. Elderly men had to be over 60 years old, while women had to be over 50 years old (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p. 3, 1946).

Again, in response the Prime Minister's office forwarded the Red Cross request to the Executive Committees of the districts, reiterating that priority should be given to the widowed parents of martyrs and victims of the War (regarding children for orphanages). This time they added the parents (and children) of those engaged in military service. During that period, most former partisans were still mobilized due to the threats the country faced, especially from the Greek Civil War, and were inevitably experiencing economic difficulties (CSA, F. 490, Fl. 416, p. 5, 1946).

What stands out when comparing the communication from the Red Cross with the Prime Minister's office is that while the Red Cross emphasized social aspects – poverty, loneliness, lack of relatives, inability to work, and other living conditions – as the main criteria for accepting the elderly and orphans into institutions, the Prime Minister's office consistently assigned priority to the parents and children of National Liberation Antifascist Martyrs, in addition to the economic criteria applied. This might also be explained by the approach of the Red Cross's chairman, who, as mentioned earlier, was attempting to alleviate the social wounds of the country without assigning much importance to the “political biography” of those in distress – whether they belonged to the “overthrown classes” or to families of anti-fascist partisans. It should be certainly noted that the parents and children of martyrs, victims, or those in military service who were experiencing economic difficulties, had no means to take care of themselves. Thus, being given priority for shelter in nursing homes or similar institutions was not unjust; they met all the criteria for admission to these institutions. On the contrary, the priority given to this social group was a characteristic feature of the socialist regime throughout its 45-year lifespan. Here we see a contradiction in socialist regimes, which while talking about equality between citizens and the elimination of private property, recognized and even helped a certain category of citizens - in this case former partisans, parents or martyred children – to establish cultural capital, which they could use to improve their material living conditions, or to enjoy privileged treatment (Koleva 2021).

If we compare the requests for admission to nursing homes during the monarchy and the fascist occupation periods to those in socialism,

there are both commonalities and differences in the approach of state institutions and individuals. While there was no established rule in previous regimes to prioritize freedom fighters of Albania's independence and sovereignty, many of the requests at the time came from Albanians from former Yugoslavia who arrived in Albania as political refugees. They were acknowledged as freedom fighters who fought for the rights of Albanians beyond the official borders and as such were displaced from their homelands. They were now homeless, without income, and elderly. Hence, their admission to asylums was seen as a right accrued in virtue of their sacrifices. Although there is no official directive from state organs to prioritize this category, these requests were usually responded to positively (Brisku 2023: 76). This is linked to the fact that just like for the socialist regime, the National Liberation War was an important founding myth of the regime, so previous regimes also had a commendatory approach to the struggles at the beginning of the twentieth century of Albanians for independence from the Ottoman Empire, as well as to the uprisings that remained outside the official borders of the new Albanian state. Also, these regimes had recognized them as people of special merit, those who had contributed "with rifle and pen" to the National Renaissance, the war for independence or the uprising of Albanians in the territories outside the state.

Regulations for admission of the elderly to nursing homes and the documents they had to present remained fundamentally the same as those that existed during the monarchy and the fascist occupation of Albania. The bureaucracy in offices for certificates, verifications, and their approvals by local authorities continued to make the procedure quite difficult for the poor and lonely elderly who had to follow these steps, especially in a country with an overall illiteracy rate of around eighty percent, and over ninety percent among the elderly (Brisku 2023: 73).

It seems from subsequent communication that the Executive Committees of the prefectures did not take significant interest in the issue. The Red Cross informed the Prime Minister's office that apart from the Tirana district, no other district had sent the Red Cross data on the requests of the elderly for shelter in the Nursing Home in Shkodër from August to December 1946. The Chairman requested the Prime Minister's office to take this matter seriously and as a priority, and to promptly send these figures to the Red Cross leadership so that vacant spots could be allocated for each district (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p. 7, 1946).

The Prime Minister's office forwarded this request from the Red Cross to the Executive Committees of the Districts, urgently asking that

all requests and corresponding files be sent to this institution (CSA, F. 490, Fl. 416, p.10, 1946). This issue seems to have been resolved in January 1947 when it appears that the districts' requests for shelter in the nursing home in Shkodër were presented to the Red Cross leadership. The Red Cross then informed the Prime Minister's office, the Executive Committee of Shkodër district, and the directorate of the nursing home in Shkodër that admissions for the year 1947 would be twenty-four elderly individuals, distributed according to quotas by districts (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p. 10, 1947).

The analysis of the aforementioned documents demonstrates lack of attention, especially from the local administration – Executive Committees of the districts, particularly with regards to sending the lists of elderly people's requests to be accommodated in the nursing home in Shkodër, even though these were numerous. This was not the case with the lists of children to be admitted to the orphanages, which were sent. The Head of the Red Cross had to draw attention twice in order to get these documents submitted from the districts. This observation regarding the overall communication between the Red Cross, the Prime Minister's office, and the Executive Committees is notable for highlighting that, the primary focus on social care for those affected by the war was on the orphaned children – mostly children of martyrs or war victims—with care for poor and solitary elderly people taking a secondary position.

It is interesting that over fourty years after the war, in 1986, the "Shqipëria e Re" Film Studio – a replica of Mosfilm in Albania – produced a film specifically addressing the issue of children left homeless and with no family after losing their parents in the war, and having to shelter in state homes. The film captured scenes of war destruction and the plight of these orphaned children, ultimately taken care of by the state, but nowhere did it show the left-behind, uncared-for and poor elders (Erebara & Haxhihyseni, 1986). In other films of this studio addressing war themes and particularly the post-war years, while the theme of the killing of partisans and civilians by the invaders is foregrounded, including depictions of the orphaned children and material damage caused by the war, there is no mention of the elderly left alone and uncared for after the war. This indicates at best a lack of attention, especially in public discourse, from the regime toward this social group. It is important to note that artistic and documentary films, as openly proclaimed by the regime, were its primary tools of propaganda to reach the masses (Anagnosti 2009).

Another notable aspect observed in the archives is that despite the numerous requests to be admitted to the nursing home in Shkodër, though the exact number is not specified in the documents but referred to as “numerous” (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p.1, 1946), the actual capacity of this nursing home which was managed by the Red Cross but ultimately under the Albanian state, was limited. The facility’s capacity was up to 120 residents. However, in January 1947, it is stated that only twenty-four individuals would be admitted, which were to be selected by the apparatus of the Executive Committees of the districts (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p. 10, 1947).

Leon Trotsky’s critique of Stalinist regimes in 1930s Soviet Union can be extended to similar critiques of Stalinist regimes in post-war socialist countries, including post-war Albania. He delves into how a state presumed to represent workers degenerates into a despotic-bureaucratic regime, where the primary economic and political power lies with the state bureaucracy and party elites. In such systems, the instruments of coercion—the police, army, secret service—are immensely powerful. Trotsky attributes this phenomenon to the scarcity and constant lack of adequate material goods and services under Stalinism, which necessitates their rationing and the selective privileging of certain social groups to access these goods and services more or with greater priority compared to the rest of the population (Trotsky 1972: 86-90).

This rationing and categorization of citizens’ access to goods and services that ideally should be accessible to everyone increases the power of the bureaucracy to distribute these resources, along with the apparatus of coercion that guarantees their distribution. Trotsky illustrates this by using the example of queues in a store – a characteristic feature of Stalinist regimes. To paraphrase, if goods in a store are scarce, queues form to purchase them, and to maintain order in the queue, a police officer needs to be deployed, further reinforcing the power of the bureaucracy and the apparatus of coercion (Trotsky 1972: 120-126).

If we refer to Leon Trotsky’s thesis that in Stalinist regimes bureaucracy gains power when goods and services are scarce, and it is granted the right to distribute these goods, the phenomena observed in the case above become clear. During the years 1945 – 1948, Albania was divided into ten districts, which meant an average quota of 2.4 individuals, who could be sheltered at the nursing home, per district – quotas were actually distributed based on the population of each district, but this is an average figure. The requests for admission to care institutions were significantly higher than these quotas. In this instance, it becomes evident

how the power of state and party bureaucratic apparatuses is strengthened, as they determined which of these elderly individuals would be admitted to the nursing home.

On the other hand, it is noticeable that in the early years of the regime, the biological link – being a parent or child, especially in the case of war orphans – associated with the National Liberation War martyrs began to crystallize as a category granting priority in the enjoyment of certain rights that were supposed to be universally available to all citizens. It is intriguing that in the early stages of the Albanian regime (until 1957), bread, food, and other consumer products were rationed, yet the rationing system was not linked as much to a person's past as it was to the nature of their work. Those engaged in harder labor were entitled to larger quantities of food. However, in the final years of the regime, in 1983, due to the state's financial difficulties, the rationing system was reintroduced, yet this time, categorization was based not on an individual's work (apart from the higher party bureaucracy) but rather on the family they belonged to. Families of war martyrs, war veterans, socialist heroes, were assigned a higher rationing category (Civici 2019: 132).

Since there are no biographies available for the residents living in the nursing home in Shkodër, it is challenging to obtain biographical data. However, based on the admission regulations of the asylum it can be inferred that, firstly, they were elderly individuals without children or close relatives they could live with. Additionally, they lacked any other financial means such as property or inheritance. Considering the majority of the admission applications arriving at this institution were mostly undersigned with a fingerprint in ink, it is plausible to infer that the majority of these elderly individuals were illiterate. Although religion is not recorded on the list, what emerges from the nominal list of those admitted into the nursing home, is that the majority of them are Muslims, with a significant presence of Catholics too. This is understandable considering that the northern part of Albania, where there is a higher concentration of Catholics in the country, has historically experienced greater poverty than other regions.

Living Conditions and Treatment in Social Care Institutions

The living conditions and nutritional provision in social care institutions were significantly impacted by the economic hardship Albania faced during the 1940s and 1950s, marked by severe shortages of basic food staples such as bread, flour, rice, oil, and other essential food items. The bread ration for an individual during this period was 300 grams per

day which, coupled with shortages in other food items, created considerable difficulties. These hardships were reflected in social care institutions such as canteens, hostels, orphanages, nursing homes, and military messes, where the nutritional provision was relatively better than that for the general population.

However, issues persisted, as evident in official communications between the Red Cross leadership and the management of the Tirana orphanage and that of the nursing home in Shkodër. The residents of these institutions expressed dissatisfaction with the insufficient quantity of food, which often resulted in them going hungry. The situation had deteriorated to the point of protests and disturbances by orphanage children who complained to every visitor about the lack of bread (CSA, F.589, Fl.10, p. 1, 1946). Similarly, elderly residents in nursing homes complained about the inadequate food supply.

As an urgent measure, Tirana's orphanage proposed an increase in bread quantities for children. They highlighted that whenever they had the opportunity to provide more bread, there were no complaints. Consequently, they requested special authorization to purchase larger quantities of bread from the bakery. The Red Cross leadership responded positively to the orphanage management's request and asked the Ministry of Economy to allow the orphanage to buy additional bread, seeing as workers hostels and student dormitories were allowed to purchase extra quantities as well (CSA, F.598, Fl.10, p. 2, 1946).

Similar complaints were directed to the Red Cross leadership by the management of the nursing home in Shkodër. In a letter dated November 1946, the nursing home administration raised the issue to the Red Cross leadership, stating that until November 1, 1946, the Economic Section in Shkodër was providing 600 grams of bread per person to the nursing home, which was still twice the amount an ordinary citizen received outside the institution. However, starting from the beginning of November of that year, the Section had reduced the quantity to 400 grams, which was still more than the quantity received by ordinary citizens. Throughout November, the institution's management had attempted to fulfill these needs with other food items such as rice, pasta, and potatoes. Yet, as they were unable to secure these food items, they requested a return to the previous quantity of 600 grams of bread. This was because there was dissatisfaction among the elderly residents, who had even protested at the nursing home management's office (CSA, F.598, Fl. 10, p. 5, 1946).

However, the Red Cross chairman responded to the nursing home management in Shkodër, indicating that the management should note that the current bread ration for the elderly residents in the home was more than what was provided to ordinary citizens, and this was deemed sufficient for them. Concerning the elderly residents' dissatisfaction with the lack of food, the leadership reminded the management that they should better understand their role not only as directors and administrators of the institution but also as executives of the new government's measures concerning the elderly. They needed to make it clear to the elderly residents that due to the country's economic difficulties, it was impossible to provide more food, and like all citizens, the elderly also needed to make sacrifices (CSA, F.598. Fl. 10, p. 6, 1946).

These documents appear to show that in the two somewhat similar situations arising in the Tirana orphanage and the Shkodër nursing home regarding complaints about insufficient food, the respective management of each relayed these concerns to the Red Cross leadership. On the other hand, although the subject is similar, the responses from the Red Cross leadership differ for these otherwise somewhat similar cases. While the request regarding the orphanage children is accepted and the Red Cross sets to fulfill it, to the elderly in the nursing home, it is explained that it is impossible to increase their food rations. The reasons for this could be diverse; firstly, the age of the orphanage children – eight to fourteen years old – who might have more immediate nutritional needs. Even students in hostels or young volunteers in actions received larger food quantities than the general population. Meanwhile, the elderly in the nursing home were not considered to require larger food portions compared to the rest of the population (CSA, F.598. Fl. 10, p. 6, 1946).

Another distinctive element noted in the correspondence between institutions is that, unlike the nursing home for the elderly in Shkodër, the Tirana orphanage received many visitors, including foreign representatives and both Eastern and Western newspapers, to whom these children had complained about the lack of food. The orphanage director highlighted this issue. As the Albanian socialist regime was particularly cautious, especially in its early years, about projecting a positive image abroad, they were reluctant to have the orphanage children express complaints in front of foreigners visiting the institution (CSA, F. 578, Fl. 8, p. 1, 1946).

This can certainly be interpreted as state institutions being more attentive to children, who were seen as the "future of socialism." However, while children were regarded as passive entities whose food requests

needed fulfillment to avoid embarrassment in front of visitors, the elderly were acknowledged as agents in their actions. The latter were urged to be conscious of the country's hardships and partake in the general sacrifice for the construction of socialism. This discourse on citizen sacrifices was a consistent part of the public and political discourse of the socialist regime in Albania.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that, as the documents show, the treatment of residents in these social care institutions was in line with the economic conditions of the time, even somewhat better than the standard for ordinary citizens. While we learn about the treatment of residents in these social care institutions – be it orphanages or the nursing home – from state documents, we only have an institutional perspective, whilst failing to capture the perspective of the elderly residents living in this nursing home. This is because no correspondence or diary entries on their part remain – likely due to illiteracy – as they probably did not even keep such records. Additionally, due to the passage of years, it is impossible to interview individuals who were elderly in the 1940s. The situation is somewhat simpler when it comes to the residents of the orphanages. For instance, in an interview, Dr. Filip Meshi, a distinguished Albanian veterinarian who lived in the Shkodër orphanage in the 1940s, recalls that both the food provision and clothing were quite good compared to the era's overall scarcity, noting that the institution did not experience the dire bread shortages felt across the country (Meshi 2011).

Apart from nutritional provision in social care institutions, particularly for the nursing home, another concern is the level of support with daily tasks and notably healthcare that the elderly needed and received. The staff list of the Shkodër's nursing home in 1940, during the Fascist regime, included two nurses and a resident doctor. This was deemed necessary by the then-director of the institution due to the majority of the elderly being old, often ill, and requiring constant healthcare. During the socialist period, these staff roles seem to have gone missing. In the organizational structure of the Shkodër nursing home, aside from the administrative staff – director, secretary-accountant, administrative chief – the caregiving staff included attendants, cooks, dishwashers, launderers, guards, and cleaners (CSA, F. 490, Fl. 701, p. 2, 1948).

This can be linked to the limited number of physicians and auxiliary medical staff, including assistants, midwives, and nurses, during that period in Albania. However, even during the monarchy and the Fascist occupation, Albania had a significantly limited number of physicians and auxiliary staff, even fewer than in the early years of the socialist regime.

One of the initial steps taken was the launch, through the Red Cross, of courses for nurse and midwife training, as well as sending students for medical training to countries within the Socialist Bloc.

The socialist regime had a different healthcare policy from the previous regimes. The political regimes before and during the war followed a medical policy that concentrated physicians in urban centers. Major cities had hospitals with both general practitioners and specialists, and key state institutions like nursing homes had their own medical staff. This policy fostered well-equipped clinics or hospitals in major cities staffed with qualified personnel but left rural areas underserved in terms of medical care. Although vaccination campaigns and medical visits were undertaken particularly at the onset of the fascist occupation, the socialist government aimed to expand healthcare services, especially in remote rural areas, seeking to cover the entire population. For this reason, even a single physician or nurse could not be “wasted” in an institution located in a city, as the residents of that institution could already access medical services in the city (Fischer & Schmitt 2022: 250).

This appears in subsequent communications between the Ministry of Health, the Directorate of Social Care, and the Nursing Home Directorate in Shkodër. It emphasizes that the healthcare needs of seriously ill elderly individuals must be addressed within the city’s polyclinic and hospital. Severely ill patients should be hospitalized at the city’s hospital, while those with chronic diseases requiring long-term treatment, particularly infectious diseases like tuberculosis, should be directed to sanatoriums rather than being kept in nursing homes (CSA, F.532, Fl.32, p. 4, 1949).

In 1948, Albania broke away from the tutelage of Yugoslavia, primarily due to the breakdown in relations between Stalin and Tito, and began entering the sphere of influence of the Soviet Union. Consequently, the latter was seen as the benchmark for the country’s development and the functioning of each institution. Therefore, that year, the Directorate of Social Care was established, tasked with a broad spectrum of activities covering everything from the care for war invalids and workers to food and social shelter institutions like canteens, hostels, and children’s nurseries (CSA, F.532, Fl. 1, pp. 1-8, 1948). Most of the activities previously carried out by the Red Cross were transferred to the Directorate of Social Care, an official state entity, while the Red Cross’s responsibilities were primarily limited to hygiene propaganda (Kryqi i Kuq Shqiptar n.d.).

This transition also affected the Nursing Home in Shkodër, which was no longer dependent on the Red Cross and was now under the jurisdiction of the Directorate of Social Care. According to communications at the end of 1948 between the Red Cross, the Council of Ministers, and this Directorate, this shift occurred primarily because, firstly, in the Soviet Union, nursing homes were under the authority of the Directorate of Social Care; secondly, the nursing home was a state institution and, as such, required oversight from a state body, rather than from an organization such as the Red Cross. Additionally, the Red Cross lacked the financial means to meet the needs of this institution (CSA, F.532, Fl.24, pp. 1-2, 1948).

The establishment of the Directorate of Social Care and the transfer of several institutions (including the nursing home in Shkodër) and responsibilities from the Red Cross to this directorate reflect two developments. Firstly, it reflects the increased influence of the Soviet model of institutional organization across various aspects of life, including social care. Secondly, this represents a departure from the pre-war model where the Red Cross, as an association, played a primary role in social care; now, this role is entirely and officially assumed by the state. In the case of Albania, this shift should not be understood as particularly disruptive, as throughout the monarchical regime, the fascist occupation, and even the early years of the socialist regime, the Red Cross had been under the control of state organs. During the monarchy, sisters of the monarch, were patrons of the organization, and the state was a significant contributor to its budget. However, the formal transfer of social care from an association (under state control) to the state itself reflects this transition between two periods.

With the transfer of the nursing home from the Red Cross to the Directorate of Social Care, its budget was no longer sourced from the Red Cross but rather allocated by the Ministry of Finance. Examining the budget figures for the nursing home in Shkodër, as planned by the Ministry of Finance, it becomes evident that aside from provisions for the residents' sustenance, the budget encompassed expenses for tobacco and cigarette paper, barber service, a preliminary fund for burial expenses for the elderly residents who might pass away, as well as a modest daily allowance (three Albanian Leks) for the residents of this institution, which they could use to have a coffee or any anything else on their outings. Simultaneously, the Ministry urges the management of this institution to be diligent in planning and spending these funds as no additional funding would be granted by the Ministry (CSA, F.505, Fl. 35, pp. 1-2, 1950).

The Directorate of the nursing home had requested additional funds for essential items for the residents, especially suits for men and dresses for women, shoes for both genders, hats for men, scarves for women, shirts, undergarments, and socks for both genders, as well as towels and handkerchiefs. This request was to replace the worn-out and significantly degraded condition of the clothing, shoes, undergarments, and linen that the residents had been using. In response, the Ministry of Finance partially approved the request but reduced the budget requested for clothing expenses, citing the challenging financial situation of the state which limited substantial expenses (CSA, F.505, Fl.35, pp. 8-10, 1950).

Therefore, it can be said that even in the transition of social care institutions, in this case the nursing home, from the Red Cross to the oversight of the Directorate of Social Care, there was no significant change in the internal organization of these institutions and the conditions for their residents, as their budgets still derived from the state treasury.

Another aspect that stands out from the communication between these institutions, as well as from the budget of the nursing home and its staff structure, is that while there is a notable focus on improving the material living conditions of these individuals – such as food and clothing, and health visits – there is a neglect of their emotional well-being and cultural life. Thus, while during that period Shkodër was perhaps the city with the richest cultural life in Albania, hosting amateur theaters, several cinemas, artistic groups in high schools, orchestras organizing various shows for citizens at symbolic prices, there is no mention of cultural programs or similar activities in any communications between the Nursing Home Directorate and the leadership of the Red Cross, or later with the Directorate of Social Care. There is no mention of cultural events organized for the elderly within the institution, or their organized participation in shows offered by artistic institutions in the city. Also, the budget allocations of this institution offer no provision for cultural or artistic activity, such as theater tickets or cinema for the elderly.

Moreover, this occurred at a time when amateur theater and entertainment groups were gaining significant momentum. These groups staged performances even in the most remote regions of the country as part of the socialist regime's overall efforts to culturally enrich and educate the population. It seemed that for the elderly, there was a perceived notion that they did not require such spiritual enrichment as comes from theater or cinema, nor did they need to be educated in the new moral norms, as they were nearing the end of their lives.

Another element worth noting about the nursing home is its so-called “Red Corner”. This usually referred to a room or hall within the communal living spaces in socialism, such as in dormitories, worker and volunteer dorms, military barracks, orphanages, and later even in prisons and labor camps, where there were books, musical instruments, and where activities like dance evenings, political lectures, and artistic workshops were organized, and in which residents of these institutions participated (Lebow 2010: 75). There does not seem to have been such a space within the nursing home. Additionally, there was no designated person in the institution’s structure responsible for such setups, as was the case in most of the aforementioned institutions. However, there is a high likelihood that the institution had a radio, which the elderly residents of the nursing home could use to listen to the political and cultural programming of Radio Tirana. Additionally, during that period, there were loudspeakers in public squares throughout the cities which broadcasted radio, aiming to reach citizens who could not afford such a device at home.

It is understandable that in the early stages of the regime, the state’s capacities were limited. However, for instance, in all voluntary camps working on the country’s reconstruction, there were spaces and individuals dedicated to the cultural and political education of the volunteers. Yet, for the elderly, all concerns centered around their basic needs – food, clothing, healthcare – but there was no consideration for their spiritual and emotional satisfaction.

This sort of differentiation allows room to conclude that the socialist regime did not focus much on ideological indoctrination for the elderly, as it did for other segments of society, especially for the youth and children. This was because the elderly – especially those in institutions – were perceived as a burden to the state, a group that it had to sustain until the end of their lives, rather than individuals who could significantly impact socialist society, for better or for worse.

The majority of cultural activities during the regime bore a political character. Consequently, theater, cinema, literature, and even music were ideologically aligned, serving the party in shaping “the new socialist man”. This explains the political-cultural activities in every work place, school, and youth communal living space, such as the above-mentioned “Red Corner”. Undoubtedly crucial for the general cultural growth of the population, particularly the youth, these activities contributed to their ideological alignment, shaping them as “the new socialist men.” However, for the elderly, much like in other socialist regimes, there was no endeavor to integrate them into the project for “the new man.” (Koleva &

Petrov 2023: 17) This is similar to the Albanian monarchy, which was very attentive to limiting foreign influences (even through donations for charity) on children, young people, and students, but which had little concern for the elderly.

Conclusions

This article's aim was to analyze the initial efforts of the Albanian socialist regime to address the social wounds caused by World War II in the country, with a particular focus on sheltering impoverished and solitary elderly individuals seeking refuge in the nursing home in Shkodër. The demands were much bigger than the institution's capacity afforded, which led state institutions to select who "deserved" to be sheltered there first. Consequently, the new regime established that the parents of war martyrs, as well as the children orphaned by the war, were to be prioritized for admission to residential care. Here, it becomes evident that although the new regime advocated equality as its primary principle and attacked private capital, it started to privilege a certain social group by affording them cultural capital, in this case, in virtue of the sacrifice of their children (or parents) during the National Liberation War.

The economic crisis in Albania during that period was inevitably reflected in the material conditions of the residents of these social care institutions. Although children in residential care and the elderly in the nursing home in Shkodër received a daily amount of food which was higher than what ordinary citizens got, it was still insufficient. However, while the Red Cross Leadership responded positively to the orphanage's requests for higher food allocation, justifying them with their residents' age, the elders were asked to make sacrifices during this crisis period the country was going through.

The government's focus on children as the "future of socialism" contrasted with their treatment of the elderly. While children were passively catered to, the elderly were expected to actively contribute to socialism through their sacrifices – a recurring theme in the socialist regime's discourse. Notably, healthcare provisions for the elderly, particularly in institutions like Shkodër's nursing home, shifted over time. During the Fascist era in 1940, the home had resident medical staff to address the constant healthcare needs of the elderly. However, these positions appear to have been reduced during the socialist period.

The interaction among various institutions and the administration, including budget allocations and staff structure at the nursing home, demonstrated a stark disparity. While considerable attention was given to

improving the material conditions of the residents – including food, clothing, and healthcare – there was a profound neglect of their emotional well-being and cultural engagement. For the elderly, there seemed to be a presumption that they neither required nor desired cultural enrichment or education in new moral norms as they were nearing the end of their lives.

The regime's treatment of the elderly stands in stark contrast to its attention to ideological indoctrination for youth and children. The majority of cultural activities during that time were politically aligned and served to shape the "new socialist man." However, these efforts largely omitted the elderly, considering them more as a burden that the state needed to sustain rather than as individuals capable of influencing socialist society. This differential treatment echoes similar practices in other socialist regimes, where cultural activities primarily focused on the youth and children's ideological alignment, neglecting the elderly's cultural and emotional fulfillment.

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